

COMPOSITE GYPSUM MATERIALS FOR THE PRODUCTION OF THERMAL INSULATION PRODUCTS: DEVELOPMENT, PROPERTIES, AND APPLICATIONS

Mustafaqulov Javohir, assistant

Kurbanov Zavkiddinjon, senior teacher

Jizzax Polytechnic Institute, Department of "Building Materials and Structures", Javohirmustafakulov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13902276>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 21-sentabr 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 23-sentabr 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 30-sentabr 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

Gypsum composites, thermal insulation, construction materials, fiber-reinforced gypsum, sustainability, energy efficiency

ABSTRACT

This thesis investigates the development of composite gypsum materials designed for thermal insulation in modern construction. The research focuses on enhancing the thermal, mechanical, and environmental properties of gypsum through the addition of fibers, polymers, and lightweight aggregates. By exploring the influence of these additives, the study identifies the optimal composition for thermal insulation products. The results demonstrate that composite gypsum materials exhibit improved thermal resistance, mechanical strength, and durability, making them suitable for sustainable construction practices. Future research directions include the incorporation of eco-friendly additives and testing long-term performance in varying environmental conditions.

Introduction

Thermal insulation plays a critical role in energy-efficient construction, reducing energy consumption for heating and cooling buildings. In the pursuit of sustainable solutions, gypsum-based materials have gained attention for their inherent fire resistance, ease of availability, and eco-friendly properties. However, traditional gypsum has limitations in thermal conductivity, prompting the development of composite materials that enhance its insulation properties while maintaining structural integrity.

Composite gypsum materials, which include fibers, lightweight aggregates, and polymers, are emerging as promising candidates for thermal insulation in construction. These materials are designed to improve the thermal performance of gypsum, reduce energy consumption, and promote sustainability in building practices. This research investigates the development, properties, and potential applications of composite gypsum materials for thermal insulation products.

Research Objectives

The key objectives of this research are as follows:

To develop and optimize composite gypsum materials for thermal insulation.

To evaluate the thermal, mechanical, and environmental performance of these materials.

To explore potential applications of composite gypsum materials in sustainable construction.

With global emphasis on reducing energy consumption and carbon footprints, there is a need for advanced materials that support green building initiatives. Gypsum, due to its low environmental impact and availability, presents an ideal material for sustainable development. By enhancing its properties through composite formulations, gypsum-based materials can offer better thermal insulation, longer lifespan, and improved durability in construction applications.

Literature Review

Properties of Gypsum in Construction

Gypsum has been used for centuries as a building material, mainly in plaster, wallboards, and fireproofing products. It is favored for its fire resistance, non-toxicity, and ease of application. However, traditional gypsum has limitations in terms of strength and thermal performance, which restricts its use in high-performance insulation products.

Advancements in Composite Gypsum Materials

Recent advancements in composite materials have introduced fibers, lightweight aggregates, and polymers to improve the properties of gypsum. Fiber reinforcement, particularly using glass fibers or polypropylene, improves the mechanical strength and reduces the risk of cracking. Lightweight aggregates, such as perlite or vermiculite, are incorporated to reduce density and improve thermal insulation properties. These additions allow for the production of gypsum-based materials that are suitable for thermal insulation and load-bearing applications.

Sustainability and Energy Efficiency in Construction

As the demand for energy-efficient and environmentally friendly materials grows, the construction industry is shifting towards sustainable building products. Composite gypsum materials align with this trend by offering improved insulation performance, thus reducing the energy required for heating and cooling buildings. Additionally, gypsum's recyclability and low carbon footprint make it an attractive option for eco-conscious construction projects.

Methodology

Materials and Formulation

The composite gypsum materials developed in this study were based on natural gypsum powder, combined with polymer binders, fibers (glass or polypropylene), and lightweight aggregates (perlite and vermiculite). Different formulations were prepared by varying the proportions of these additives, with the aim of optimizing thermal and mechanical properties.

Testing Procedures

To evaluate the performance of the composite gypsum materials, a series of tests were conducted:

Thermal Conductivity: The thermal insulation properties were measured using a guarded hot plate apparatus to assess the materials' ability to resist heat transfer.

Mechanical Strength: Compressive strength and flexural strength tests were carried out following ASTM standards to determine the materials' load-bearing capacity.

Environmental Resistance: The samples were subjected to humidity, freeze-thaw cycles, and temperature variations to test their durability in different climatic conditions.

Data Analysis

The results from the thermal and mechanical tests were analyzed to identify the relationship between the composition of the gypsum composites and their performance. Statistical analysis was used to compare the effects of different additives and determine the optimal formulation for thermal insulation products.

Results and Discussion

Thermal Performance of Composite Gypsum

The results showed that the addition of lightweight aggregates and fibers significantly reduced the thermal conductivity of the gypsum composites. Among the tested formulations, those with higher perlite content demonstrated the best insulation performance, reducing

heat transfer by up to 30% compared to traditional gypsum. This indicates that composite gypsum materials are suitable for use in thermal insulation panels and other energy-efficient building products.

Mechanical Properties

The mechanical strength of the composite gypsum materials was enhanced by the inclusion of fibers. Samples with glass fiber reinforcement exhibited higher compressive and flexural strength compared to those without fibers. This improvement ensures that the composite materials can be used in both structural and insulation applications, providing thermal benefits without compromising load-bearing capacity.

Environmental Resistance

The environmental testing revealed that composite gypsum materials performed well under exposure to moisture and temperature fluctuations. Fiber-reinforced samples, in particular, showed better resistance to cracking and deformation, making them suitable for use in regions with extreme weather conditions. The freeze-thaw resistance of the composites was also significantly improved compared to traditional gypsum products.

Implications for Sustainable Construction

Composite gypsum materials offer several advantages for sustainable construction. Their enhanced thermal insulation properties contribute to reduced energy consumption in buildings, while their mechanical strength allows for diverse applications in both residential and commercial projects. The use of recyclable materials, such as gypsum and certain polymers, further supports green building initiatives.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that composite gypsum materials, when reinforced with fibers and lightweight aggregates, offer superior thermal insulation and mechanical properties compared to traditional gypsum. These materials are well-suited for applications in energy-efficient construction, contributing to reduced energy consumption and supporting sustainable building practices.

Future Research Directions

Future research should focus on the long-term durability of composite gypsum materials, particularly under harsh environmental conditions. Additionally, the development of bio-based additives and further optimization of formulations will enhance the sustainability of these materials. Exploring new applications, such as integration with phase-change materials (PCMs) for enhanced thermal regulation, could also provide valuable advancements in the field of insulation technology.

REFERENCES

1. Курбанов, З. Х., & Талипов, Н. Х. (2024). ОБЛИЦОВОЧНЫЙ ПЛИТОЧНЫЙ КЛЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ЦЕМЕНТА НИЗКОЙ ВОДОПОТРЕБНОСТИ.
2. Бердиев, О. Б., Курбанов, З. Х., & Абдурахманов, А. (2023). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТРЕБУЕМОЙ ТЕПЛОПРОВОДНОСТИ ПО НОРМАТИВНЫМ ДОКУМЕНТАМ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ГОРОДА ДЖИЗАК (РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН): ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТРЕБУЕМОЙ ТЕПЛОПРОВОДНОСТИ ПО НОРМАТИВНЫМ ДОКУМЕНТАМ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ГОРОДА ДЖИЗАК (РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН).
3. Бердиев, О. Б., Болотов, Т. Т., Мамиров, А. Х., & Курбанов, З. Х. (2023). БЫСТРОТВЕРДЕЮЩЕЙ СУЛЬФАТСОДЕРЖАЩЕЙ ДОБАВКИ ДЛЯ САМОВЫРАВНИВАЮЩИХСЯ ПОЛОВ: БЫСТРОТВЕРДЕЮЩЕЙ СУЛЬФАТСОДЕРЖАЩЕЙ ДОБАВКИ ДЛЯ САМОВЫРАВНИВАЮЩИХСЯ ПОЛОВ.

4. Бердиев, О., Талипов, Н., Курбонов, З., & Болотов, Т. (2023). Development of a formulation for dry cement-adhesive dry building mixtures for ceramic slabs using the addition of spent alumina catalysts. *Scientific Collection «InterConf»*, (180), 407-414.
5. Kurbanov, Z., & Artiqqulov, D. (2023). DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF DRY CONSTRUCTION MIXED ON THE BASIS OF LOCAL MARBLE WASTE POWDER. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(9), 104-106.
6. Hamidulloevich, K. Z. (2023). DETERMINATION OF THE CONTENT OF DRY CONSTRUCTION MIXED ON THE BASIS OF LOCAL MARBLE WASTE POWDER. *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 273-275.
7. Kurbanov, Z., & Artiqqulov, D. (2023). OPPORTUNITIES TO GET LIGHT SUPPLIES BASED ON COAL WASTE. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(9), 100-103.
8. Курбанов, З., & Ортиккулов, Д. (2023). ВЫСОКОПРОЧНЫЙ ГИПСОВЫЙ ВЯЖУЩИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ СУЛЬФАТСОДЕРЖАЩЕГО ОТХОДА. *Models and methods in modern science*, 2(2), 5-12.
9. Талипов, Н., Курбанов, З., & Артыккулов, Д. (2023). ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СУХИЕ СМЕСИ С ПОЛИМЕРНЫМИ ДОБАВКАМИ. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(5), 43-48.
10. Шоқосимов, И. К., & Курбанов, З. Х. (2021). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА ЗЕМЛЯНЫХ РАБОТ С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ГЕОСЕТОК.
11. Rahmonqul O'g'li, M. J. (2023). KUL-SHLAKLI ARALASHMASIDAN QURILISH MATERIALLARINI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA QO'LLASH. *Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences*, 269-271.
12. Қурбонов, З., Эшқулов, Н., & Ортиққулов, Д. (2023). ҚУРУҚ ҚУРИЛИШ ҚОРИШМАЛАРИНИНГ АСОСИЙ ТАРКИБИЙ ҚИСМЛАРИ. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(5), 61-66.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY